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EDITORIAL NOTE

It is with immense pleasure and pride that we present to you the third issue of the Bauchi State University (BASUG) Law Journal, marking our second publication for the year. This issue stands as a testament to the tireless commitment of our contributors, whose scholarly work continues to push the boundaries of legal scholarship in Nigeria and beyond.

We are particularly elated by the diversity and depth of the submissions received for this edition, not only from across Nigeria but also from international scholars. The topics covered reflect the evolving and multifaceted nature of legal discourse in our contemporary society.

These papers, among others, cover a vast range of legal fields, reflecting the dynamic interplay between law and society. We believe the breadth of scholarship featured in this issue will contribute meaningfully to academic discourse and legal practice.

We would like to extend our profound appreciation to the Faculty of Law, Sa'adu Zungur University, for their unwavering support as our publisher. Our sincere gratitude also goes to the Management of Sa'adu Zungur University for their continued encouragement and partnership in ensuring the success of this journal.

We are deeply indebted to the contributing authors for their invaluable research and dedication to advancing legal knowledge. Their work remains at the heart of what makes this journal a beacon of academic excellence.

Finally, we thank you, our esteemed readers, for your continued engagement with the BASUG Law Journal. It is through your readership that this publication finds purpose, and we hope that this issue serves as both a valuable resource and a source of inspiration for future legal thought and action.

Sincerely,

Prof. S. M. G Kanam
Chairman of Editorial Board and Dean
Faculty of Law,
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**ADVANCING CHILDREN'S RIGHTS IN NIGERIA: ANALYZING
THE EFFECTIVENESS OF KANO STATE'S CHILD
PROTECTION LAW, 2023 AMIDS SOCIO-CULTURAL AND
GENDER CHALLENGES**

By

Aisha Ali Tijjani,¹

Abstract

The Kano State Child Protection Law, 2023, was passed recently at the tail end of the previous administration. The law was passed after persisting pressures from the citizens of the State to protect the rights of the child, promote and safe-guarding the life and welfare of the child, preventing the child from any form of exploitation, abuse, violence or anything done to the child that is not in his/her best interest and at the same time punishes any perpetrator irrespective of the relationship whatsoever he/she has with the child. This study critically examines the Kano State Child Protection Law, 2023, focusing on the challenges to its effective implementation from a gender perspective. Despite the law's progressive provisions aimed at safeguarding children's rights, its enforcement faces significant obstacles, including political inertia, cultural and religious resistance, poverty, and societal misconceptions. The research employs a doctrinal method, analyzing legal texts, case law, and cultural practices to identify and examine these barriers. Findings reveal that religious organizations and socio-cultural norms considerably hinder the law's practical application. The paper advocates for increased awareness, civic engagement, and legal reforms to foster better enforcement and realization of children's rights in Kano State. Ultimately, the study underscores that the future development of Nigeria depends on how effectively its children's rights are protected and promoted today.

Keywords: *advocacies, child rights, cultural/religious practices, enactment*

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

Violence against children is a global phenomenon that has become a worrisome subject matter. It has attracted the attention of concerned government and non-governmental organizations, international and local human rights bodies, religious instructors and concerned individuals. This is due to the escalating occurrences of violence being perpetrated across the globe. Usually, facts on violence against children, are those that emanate from reported incidences alone. A simple imaginary question that comes to mind here is what about those unreported cases being perpetrated in private which are not being reported yet more rampant, but the victims remain silent due to fear of social stigma, lack of appropriate record system, concealment of facts of with security agencies. Building social protection to reduce risks related to developmental and life-cycle of vulnerabilities is crucial, particularly in the context of developing country and is now increasingly recognized in mainstream development circles.² The concept of human rights has become increasingly important since the end of World War II³ due to the atrocities arising from the wars which gave renewed impetus to the doctrine and political significance of human rights globally.⁴ As a result of global wars which ended in 1945, some efforts, steps and measures were taken to restore, revamp and regain the dignity of human person.⁵ These measures were in the form of adoption of several international instruments such as the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) 1948, International Convention on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) 1981⁶; and host of others including the United Nations Child Rights Convention (UNCRC) 1989, which forms the basis of this paper. The United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child was adopted by the United Nations General Assembly in 1989.⁷ The convention affirms children's entitlement to

² N. Jones, et al, 'Promoting Synergy between Child Protection and Social Protection in Nigeria', Overseas Development Institute (ODI) and UNICEF, Nigeria, (February 2012), www.odi.org.uk pdf (accessed on the 1st October, 2024 at 11:00am) 1

³ E. I. Alemika and S. K. Kigbu, "Translating the Legal Framework on the Rights of Child (Child Rights Act 2003) into Effective Practice Through Human Rights Education in Nigeria", (2010), www.ihrec2015.org/panel%2010 pdf (accessed on the 1st October, 2024 at 11:32am) 2

⁴ Ibid

⁵ Ibid

⁶ Ibid

⁷ A. A. Francis, et al, 'Law and Children's Right Protection: the Nexus for a Sustainable Development in Nigeria', Canadian Social Science, (Vol. 6), (No.2), (2010), www.cscanada.net or www.cscanada.org pdf (accessed on the 1st October, 2024 at 11: 51am) 27

development, protection, participation and non-discrimination;⁸ it also acknowledges that the realization of these rights for children can only be accomplished through the care and assistance of adults.⁹ Nigeria ratified the UN Convention on Rights of Children in 1991. This implies that henceforth, the country had committed itself to a code of binding obligations towards her children.¹⁰ This is because in Nigeria, violence against children has gained increasing visibility as a critical human right and public health challenge. UNICEF estimated that over 60% of children suffer sexual, physical and other kinds of violation in Nigerian society.¹¹ Among the prominent social vices and crimes connected with violence in Kano state is child abuse. This is a serious menace that undermines child's right in the state particularly and other parts of Nigeria. Statistically, facts revealed in some researches regarding crimes perpetrated against children in Kano state is a pellucid testimony.¹²

This article studies this phenomenon, marking Kano state as a case study. It finds that Kano state, due to influence of culture and unavailability of effective legal implementation mechanisms, is unfortunately, due to lack of utility and recognition to the law, a leading example on case of violent practices against children. The objective of this article is to investigate the reason why despite the enactment of the child's protection law, 2023 in Kano state, occurrences are still high. It is also the objective of this article to find out the challenges that hinder the successful implementation of the law. Using doctrinal research methodology, the paper will use the primary sources of law namely; Nigerian legislations and case laws to discuss the various definitions of a child in the contexts examines the basic provisions of the Child Rights Act, 2003, highlights some of the challenges facing the applicability of the Act in some many states in Nigeria, makes some recommendations and conclusion. This research is

⁸ O. U. Odera, 'Knowledge and Awareness of the Child's Rights Act among Residents of a University Town in Enugu State, Nigeria', *Educational Research* (ISSN: 2141 - 5161), (Vol. 2(10), (October, 2011), PP 1595-1601. www.interestjournals.org/ER/pdf (accessed on the 1st October, 2016 at 12:00pm) 1595

⁹ R. K., Awosola, et al, 'Child Rights and the Media: the Nigerian Experience ', *Stud Home Comm Sci*, 2 (2): 125-131 (2008) www.krepublishers.com/HCS-02-2-125-131.pdf (accessed on the 1st October, 2024 at 12:14 pm) 125

¹⁰ Ibid

¹¹ *Today newspaper*: September 24, 2016

¹² M.I., Yelwa, 'Violence against women and children in Kano state and strategies for its prevention: An overview, *Bayero Journal of Private and Commercial Law*, a peer reviewed journal of the department of private and commercial law, faculty of law, BUK, (BJPCL), (Vol.3), 1, (June, 2020)

undoubtedly of high importance because it is going to unveil the challenges that bedeviled the proper implementation of the law.

2.0 Theoretical framework: human right and socio-cultural theory

A right is an authority residing in a person against another and that right becomes enforceable only when it is recognized by the state and the state must, ensure it's in the sense, a right is a creation of the legal system. The concept of human right is the modern version of what was originally known as natural rights. Natural law has been defined or described as a higher law to which every other law must conform in order to be valued. It is also ascribed to have a divine origin. It is a body of rules imposed on mankind by nature; these rules are independent of any man-made laws.¹³

2.1 The human rights theory¹⁴

This is a framework that explains the fundamental rights and freedoms inherent to all human beings, regardless of nationality, ethnicity, gender, or status. These rights are considered universal, inalienable, and indivisible. Different types of human right include; civil and political rights which covers freedom of speech, assembly, and associations; right to life, liberty and security on the one hand and economic, social and cultural rights which cover right to education, healthcare, work, and social security on the other hand. Some of the human right theories are:

1. Natural Rights Theory: Human rights are derived from natural law and are inherent to human nature.

2. Social Contract Theory: Human rights are based on agreements between individuals and governments.

3. Human Dignity Theory: Human rights are rooted in the inherent dignity and worth of every human being.

The major Importance of human right theories is that they provide a foundation for understanding and promoting human rights, which are essential for building just and equitable societies. Others include;

1. Protection: Human rights protect individuals from abuse, exploitation, and oppression.

¹³ S. E., Kabo, 'Enforcing the Rights of a Muslim Child in Nigeria: Conflicts Between the Child's Right Act and Islamic Law', *Bayero Journal of Islamic Law*, (Vol.2),1, (September, 2018)38

¹⁴ J.N., Sambo, 'Fundamental Concepts of Jurisprudence', (3rd Edition, Bookmakers Publishing), (2007), 4

2. Empowerment: Human rights empower individuals to claim their rights and participate in decision-making.
3. Promoting dignity: Human rights promote human dignity, equality, and justice.

2.2 Socio-cultural theory¹⁵

This theory emphasizes the role of social interactions, culture, and context in shaping human behavior, cognition, and development. It suggests that people learn and develop through interactions with others, and that culture influences how we think, feel, and behave. Some of the Key aspects of the theory are:

1. Social interaction: Learning and development occur through interactions with others.
2. Cultural context: Culture shapes our values, beliefs, and practices.
3. Contextual influence: Environment and context influence behavior and cognition.

Some of the Applications of the theory are:

1. Education: Understanding how students learn from teachers, peers, and cultural context.
 2. Psychology: Examining how social and cultural factors influence human behavior.
 3. Anthropology: Studying how culture shapes human behavior and cognition.
- Notable among these theorists is Lev Vygotsky who developed the concept of scaffolding and the zone of proximal development. Socio-cultural theory helps us understand how social and cultural factors shape human behavior and development.

2.3 Who is a Child?

As it is with most of the Social Science concepts, they hardly get a universally acceptable definition; the definition of a child is in no way different. Divergent and conflicting definitions and age limits were given by various Nigerian Legislations with the aim of determining the age of a child,¹⁶ the lack of uniformity in the definition

¹⁵ G., Ezejiofor, 'The Development of the Concept of Human Rights: Definition and Philosophical Foundations, in A. O., Obilade & C. Nwankwo, (Eds), 'Text for Human Right Teaching in Schools, (Constitutional right project), (1999)5

¹⁶ O. S. Akinwumi (2009), "Legal Impediments on Practical Implementation of the Child Rights Act, 2003", International Journal of Legal Information: Volume 37: Iss. 3, Article 10. www.scholarship.law.cornell.edu/ijli/vol37/iss3/10 pdf (accessed on the 1st October, 2024 at 9: 20pm) 387

extends to Islamic Law, Customary Law and even the Common Law applicable in the country.¹⁷ In some ethnic groups, a boy remains a child until initiated into an age-grade society or until he is old enough to contribute physically and financially to community development. But in some societies, childhood terminates at puberty.¹⁸ At common law, the age of puberty in respect of a boy is fourteen (14) years, while a girl is considered to have attained puberty at twelve (12) years. Thus, in *Harrod v. Harrod*,¹⁹ under the customary law there is no fixed minimum age of puberty. For Yoruba, the age of puberty is fourteen (14) for a girl and seventeen (17) for boys,²⁰ while for Hekiris, it is sixteen (16) for girls and twenty (20) for boys.²¹

Section 2 of the Children and Young Persons Act²² defines a child as a person under the age of fourteen (14) while a young person is a person who is above the age of fourteen (14) but under the age of seventeen (17) years. The Nigerian Labour Act²³ considers a child as a person below the age of fifteen (15), National Child Welfare Policy²⁴ defines a child as anybody who is twelve (12) years of age and below, Immigration Act stipulates that any person below the age of sixteen (16) is a minor, whereas Matrimonial Causes Act puts the age of maturity at twenty-one (21) (anybody below 21 is a child).²⁵ Section 50 of the Penal Code (Northern) States that: “No act is an offence which is done by a child under seven years of age; or by a child above seven years of age but under twelve years of age who has not attained sufficient maturity of understanding to judge the nature and consequence of such act.” However in line with the convention on the rights of the child (CRC) and the African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child both to which Nigeria is a signatory, section 16 of the Child Protection of Law of Kano State ²⁶ finally laid to rest the uncertainty trailing the

¹⁷ A. A. Francis, et al, (n. 6) 28

¹⁸ Ibid

¹⁹ (1954) 69 ER 344

²⁰ A. A. Francis, et al, (n. 6), 28

²¹ Ibid

²² 1933

²³ 1974

²⁴ 1989

²⁵ F. D. Nzarga, ‘Impediments to the Domestication of Nigeria Child Rights Act by the States’, *Journal of Culture, Society and Development*, (Vol. 19), (2016) [www.iiste.org pdf](http://www.iiste.org/pdf) (accessed 1st October, 2024 at 11:17pm) 48

²⁶ 2023

definition of a child under the Nigerian Laws. It defines a child as a person as who has not attained the age of puberty without specification of years.²⁷ This definition will tend to suit and be compatible with a lot of definitions above.

3.0 Historical Development of the Child Rights in Nigeria

The convention on the Rights of the Child enjoins that the principles contained in the conventions be disseminated by the member states and take all appropriate legislative measures for the implementation of the rights recognized therein.²⁸ The general frameworks within which human rights are protected in Nigeria are enshrined in the 1999 constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (as amended). Chapter IV contains an elaborate Bill of Rights.²⁹ In 1996, Nigeria submitted its first report on the implementation of the Child Rights Convention to the United Nations Committee on the Rights of the Child.³⁰ The committee recommends among other things, that, for Nigeria to realize full implementation of the Child Rights under the Nigerian Laws, it has to domesticate the Child Rights Convention.³¹ Domestication of the convention and subsequent enactment of the Child Rights Act 2003 has generated a lot of discussions and criticisms from left, right and centre of the country, ranging from Islamic values, traditions and culture.³²

Finally, the Child Rights Act was adopted in September, 2003,³³ albeit only few out of the 36 states in Nigeria passed the Child Rights Act into law, due to religious, traditional and cultural reasons.³⁴ Kano state passed its own law in May, 2023.

²⁷ A. A. Francis, et al, (n. 6) , 28

²⁸ O. S. Akinwumi, (n.16), 386

²⁹ E. I. Alemika and S. K. Kigbu, (n.2), 2

³⁰ Nigeria Convention on the Rights of the Child: Second Country Periodic Report (2004), Federal Ministry of Women Affairs, Abuja www.ohchr.org/pdf (accessed on the 2nd October, 2024 at 9:24pm) 12 of 163

³¹ CRC, Concluding Observation of the Committee on the Rights of the Child, CRC/C/15/Add.61 30/10/96; also [www.unhcr.ch/tbs/doc.nsf\(symbol\)-crc.c.15Add1En?openDocument](http://www.unhcr.ch/tbs/doc.nsf(symbol)-crc.c.15Add1En?openDocument); see also section 12 of the constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended) on the requirement for domestication of foreign articles and conventions. The author(s) should avoid repetition and ensure a consistent referencing style (NALT Citation style)

³² A. Sirajo and I. U. Zwall, 'Child Protection System and Community Policing', *European Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, (Vol. 13), (No. 1), 2012 www.journalsBank.com/pdf (accessed on the 2nd October, 2016 at 10:09 pm) 627

see also O. U. Odera, (n.7), 159 and R. K. Awosola, (n. 8), 125

³³ www.unice.org/wcaro/WACRAD_Nigeria_factsheets.pdf (accessed on the 2nd October, 2016 at 10:27pm) page 2

³⁴ O. S. Akinwumi, (n. 16), 386

4.0 Basic Provisions of the Kano State Child’s Protection Law, 2023

The Law recognizes the freedom of a girl child from discrimination on grounds of belonging to a particular community or ethnic group, place of origin, sex, religion, the deprivation of forming a political opinion; and it is stated categorically that the dignity of the child shall be respected at all times.³⁵ The Law further guarantees the right of a Child to recreation, rest, leisure and enjoyment of the best attainable state of physical, mental and spiritual health.³⁶

The Law also provides for the less privileged as well as mentally or physically challenged, street children, orphans, abandoned, and victims of violence (sexual violence and torture inclusive).³⁷ The basic provisions of the law follows chapter IV of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as amended) with specific focus on children.³⁸

The Child’s Protection Law is an embodiment of comprehensive legislation with Twenty four (24) parts, containing 201 sections with three schedules that particularly deal with the state and local government child protection implementation committee. Financial provision pursuant to section 30(12) of the Law is provided under the second schedule and supervision of child orders pursuant to sections 32(2), 33(7) and 35(8) under the third schedule. Each part of the Act contains different topical issues on children’s interest, welfare, juvenile justice and administration³⁹ with the sole aim of providing protection, upholding and promotion of rights and needs of a child.

Part I (section 3) deals with the primacy of the best interest of the child and maintenance of the child; best interest of a child to be a paramount consideration in all actions concerning a child whether undertaken by an individual, the public, private body, institution, court of law or administration or legal authority. The section further provided that a child shall be given such protection and care as is necessary for the well-being of the child. Cognizance should be paid to the rights and duties of the child’s parents, guardians, or other individuals, institutions, service providers, agencies, organizations or bodies legally responsible for the child.

³⁵ Ibid, 388

³⁶ F. D. Zarga, (n. 25), 50

³⁷ O. S. Akinwumi, (n. 16)388

³⁸ Ibid

³⁹ Ibid, 390

Part II (sections 4 - 15) provides for the protection of the rights and responsibilities of the child in addition to those provisions under chapter IV of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as amended) or any related provisions to the fundamental human rights as if stated expressly in the Law. The section maintains that these rights and responsibilities of the child including to practice the religious persuasions shall be respected by all persons, bodies, institutions and authority. These provisions cover a range of rights specifically right to survival and development⁴⁰, rights to name⁴¹, right to dignity⁴², right to leisure and recreation⁴³, right to good health⁴⁴ that is best attainable state of physical, mental and spiritual health where by state and local government shall endeavor to reduce infant mortality rate, development of primary health care, adequate nutrition, safe drinking water, good hygiene and environmental sanitation. Other rights are right to parental care⁴⁵, right to education⁴⁶ which must be free, compulsory and universal basic education up to senior secondary school, qur'anic education, vocational/skills and trade education, right to special⁴⁷ care for a child in need of special care in such a way as to commensurate a measure of protection as appropriate to the physical, social, economic, emotional and mental needs of the child to ensure his dignity and promote his self-reliance and active participation in the affairs of the community. Right to own property⁴⁸ whether tangible or in tangible and lastly right to the unborn child⁴⁹ to protection against harm. Under this part, section 15 provides for the responsibilities of the child towards his wards, parents, guardians, communities, society and Nigeria at large.

Part III (sections 16 - 26) made certain provisions with regard to the meaning of a child and other prohibitions like that of child marriage⁵⁰, permanent tattoo and skin

⁴⁰ Section 5

⁴¹ Section 6

⁴² Section 7

⁴³ Section 8

⁴⁴ Section 9

⁴⁵ Section 10

⁴⁶ Section 11

⁴⁷ Section 12

⁴⁸ Section 13

⁴⁹ Section 14

⁵⁰ Section 16

marks⁵¹, exposure of child to use and trafficking of narcotics drugs⁵², use of child in criminal offence⁵³, abduction of child from lawful custody⁵⁴, use of child for the purpose of carrying out political activity⁵⁵, use of child for labor⁵⁶, use of child for begging and hawking⁵⁷, use of child for exploitation and prostitution and other forms of exploitation as contained under section 24 of this law. Section 25 provides for the extension of the jurisdiction of magistrate, sharia or any other court to have full jurisdiction when entertaining the issues of a child. Lastly under this part, section 16 provided for protection of children generally whether born or unborn.

Despite these prohibitions and protection, a lot of children in need are roaming around the streets of Kano including those neglected by their parents, with a high number of out of school and school drop outs, significant number of them facing risk of child labor, trafficking and abuse. While recent statistics are difficult to pinpoint, studies and reports highlight concerning trends. Child labor is prevalent, with over half of the children aged 5-17 involved, and a substantial portion below the legal working age.⁵⁸ Additionally, a large number of children are out of school, with estimates suggesting one in three children aged 6-15 are not attending school, making Kano state to be identified among the states with a high population of children particularly from rural and marginalized communities. These factors, combined with the state's high poverty rate and socio-cultural norms, exacerbates the risks of high child trafficking and abuse. A study found out that 53.6% of children in Kano between 5 and 17 years old were involved in child labor. According to UNICEF, there are documented case of child exploitation and trafficking in Nigeria, including in the northern region where Kano is located.⁵⁹

⁵¹ Section 17

⁵² Section 18

⁵³ Section 19

⁵⁴ Section 20

⁵⁵ Section 21

⁵⁶ Section 22

⁵⁷ Section 23

⁵⁸ *Daily trust facebook page*, 'accessing the phenomenon of out of schoolchildren in nigeria', (29th October, 2024)

⁵⁹ *Daily trust*, UNICEF situational analysis of out-of-school children on the rise in Kano, (3rd July 2025). <https://dailytrust.com/number-of-out-of-school-children-on-the-rise-in-Kano-study/> Last accessed 6th August, 2025 @10:55pm.

Part IV (sections 27-29) makes provisions for the protection of child in need of care. The law empowers the community organization like the *zaure*, the community development officer, the *hisbah* corps, police and any other person to take care of the child. Other supporting provisions that may not need explanation are;

Part V (sections 30 - 39) provides for rules for care and supervision of children in need;

Part VI (sections 40- 66) makes provisions on guardianship, wardship, fostering and adoption of children;

Part VII (sections 68 - 81) makes provisions for the creation of Family courts.

Part IX (sections 78-82) makes provision for support for children and families

Part X (section 83) provides for governmental support, community and voluntary homes;

Part XI (sections 84-85) makes provisions for supervisory functions and responsibility of the ministry

Part XII (sections 86-116) makes provisions for child justice administration

Part XIII (sections 117-120); makes provisions for approval institution and post-release supervision

Part XIV (sections 121-123) deals with miscellaneous matters

5.0 Challenges to Effective Operation of the Rights of the Children in Nigeria

There are numerous reasons that hinder the smooth implementation of the Child's protection law in Kano state which include among others:

(a) Political Reason:

Kano state joined the league of state that domesticated the Child Rights Act in Nigeria.⁶⁰ But the domestication is more of a lip service than real implementation of the content of the laws, this will be seen from insignificant difference on the lives of the children in the state before the domestication of the Law and it's two years now after the passage of the Law, as against the highly anticipated gains that motivated to a great extent the passage of these bills into laws.⁶¹

(b) Protest by the Supreme Council for Shari'a in Nigeria

⁶⁰ F. D. Nzarga, (n. 25), 50

⁶¹ Ibid

Soon after the Act was ratified in Nigeria, the Supreme Council for Shari'ah in Nigeria kicked against it and protested, arguing that it is an imposition by the Federal Government on States Assemblies, aiming at equating males and females in matters of inheritance, prohibiting child marriage, giving a share of inheritance to illegitimate children and establishing a family court to rob shari'ah court with jurisdiction on matters affecting children.⁶² Even at the public hearing of the bill on 1st December, 2022, some Islamic scholars at the state assembly still protested against this issue. I am a living witness to this.

(c) Child Labour

Hawking, begging and house help (“Yar/Dan Aiki”)⁶³ which have eaten deep in the roots of Northern Nigeria are all part of the politics rocking the ratification and implementation of the Child Rights Act in the Northern part of the country and especially in Kano.⁶⁴ The law in Section 22 forbids the use of a child for Alms begging, hawking, slavery and compulsory labor despite provisions for punishment.

(d) Poverty

It will be difficult to protect children's rights if there is poverty, because a poor person will use all that is within his/her disposal for survival.⁶⁵ One of the instruments for survival that are usually within the disposal of most people is/are their child/children.⁶⁶ Therefore, child labor, child prostitution and other child related vices cannot be wished away as long as poverty exists.⁶⁷ More so a lot of parents can't sponsor their children to school, the only available option is to marry off their female children at a very young age or to use them as a source of income which is detrimental to the children.

(e) Religious and Cultural Practices

⁶² Ibid

⁶³ House Help – “Yar/Dan Aiki” – These are children mostly girl-child below the age of 14 brought from rural area to an urban area to work as an errand in the houses of well to do , when their children are there schooling (Modern Slavery).

⁶⁴ F. D. Nzarga, (n.25)., 52

O. S. Akinwumi,(n.16), 393

⁶⁵ O. U. Odera, (n.7)., 1596

⁶⁶ Ibid

⁶⁷ Ibid

Some religious and cultural practices obtainable in the state have made the implementation of the Child's protection Law difficult. Religious Practices such as:

- i. Almajiri⁶⁸ Practice
- ii. Early Marriage

Early marriage and sexual abuse are complex and interconnected issues that affect millions of individuals worldwide, particularly women and girls.⁶⁹ Marriage is the beginning of an important stage in life that requires adequate preparation. Many studies have proven that early pregnancy (under 18 years of age) has risks for both the mother and the unborn child generally. This is because a healthy pregnancy free from harm and danger requires full development of both the skeleton and reproductive system so as not to expose the mother and her child to several health complications that lead to more than 70,000 deaths annually worldwide. United nations data indicates that 39,000 girls under the age of 18 years get married every day. In developing countries, one in every three girls is married before the age of 18. About 90% of these married girls are at the least likely to use family planning methods and account for the highest percentage of women with unmet need for family planning and account for 20,000 births everyday i.e 7.3 million births every year, making up 95% of teenage birth worldwide which account for 30% of obstetric fistula cases worldwide. Obstetric fistulas are among the worst complications of childbirth, affecting mothers both psychologically and physically. Patients often suffer from severe depression⁷⁰ leading to divorce or even suicide. As defined by the WHO, maternal mortality is the death of a woman while pregnant or within forty-two days of the termination of pregnancy. The study maintained that in spite of modernization, the culture of the people particularly in rural areas of Kano state, still plays a dominant role in shaping their reproductive behavior. The study reveals that, while education is likely to enhance female autonomy,

⁶⁸ Children sent from far and near their homes in the Northern Part of Nigeria and entrusted into the care of Islamic teachers to learn the Islamic Studies, who are mostly left responsible for themselves, living on their daily earnings through hard labour, begging and so many unbefitting activities for a child.

⁶⁹ Meta A1with L/R MA.3.2, last accessed on Sunday 17/11/2024=@8:19pm

⁷⁰ UNFPA, 'the state of world population 2013, motherhood in childhood: facing the challenges of adolescent pregnancy In islam's position on violence against women', international centre for population and growth, Al'azhar University,Cairo, Egypt.(n.d)(n.p)

so that women develop greater confidence and capability to make decisions about their own health in urban centers, rural women are more readily influenced by traditional practices that are contrary to the modern health practices related to maternal health. Furthermore, the study reveals that on factors affecting knowledge and utilization of maternal health facilities in Kano, particularly in the rural areas, it suggests that the traditional conception of early practice also plays a significant role in the Knowledge in maternal health service and the age at which girls are given out of marriage. 75% of the rural⁷¹ respondents at the sample areas were married at less than 18 years⁷² while 96.7% urban respondents married 18 years or above as against the 25% rural respondents. The major objective of the study is to look at the roles played by some selected cultural practices and the effects of such roles on maternal mortality in the rural areas of Kano state.

iii. Child Witches⁷³

The concept of 'child witches' is a disturbing phenomenon in some parts of the world, particularly in Africa. It refers to the accusation and persecution of children, often young girls, for alleged witchcraft. In Nigeria, it is not very common to Kano state. It is mostly common in east. Consequences attached to child witches include:

1. Abuse and violence: Children accused of witchcraft may face physical and emotional abuse, including beatings, torture, and even death.
2. Social exclusion: Accused children may be ostracized by their communities, leading to social isolation and stigma.
3. Psychological trauma: The experience can cause long-term psychological damage, affecting their mental health and well-being. One of the major Causes of witch accusations in children is Superstition and misinformation. It is believed to be a real and powerful force, leading to fear and accusations and also

⁷¹ Rural areas selected in Kano Are Bichi, Gaya, Kibiya and Shanono local government areas

⁷² A. Anifat, I.M. Msughter and S. Amali, 'Implications of some cultural practices on maternal mortality: A study of some selected rural areas of Kano state, Nigeria' *International Journal of Innovative Research & Development*, ISSN 2278-0211(online), <https://www.Internationaljournalcorner.com> last accessed 6th august,2025@ 12:15am

⁷³ This practice is common in Akwa-Ibom and Cross-Rivers of Nigeria, where self-professed pastors blame them for causing illness, death and destruction. In these states about 15,000 children have been branded child witches.

C. N. Uzuegbu, 'Culture and Child Abuse in Nigeria', *International Journal of Research in Arts and Social Sciences*, (vol.2) www.academicexcellencesociety.com pdf (accessed 11/10/2024 at 11:31am) 203

used as a means of explaining misfortune or illness. The issue of child witchcraft accusations highlights the need for continued efforts to promote children's rights, education, and protection.

(f) Cultural Practices (Cultural Relativism) ⁷⁴:

- (a) Female Genital Mutilation (FGM)
- (b) Desire for large family size
- (c) Preference for male children
- (d) Tribal Marks

6.0 Findings

- i. Children are left at the mercy of legislators;
- ii. There is lack of enlightenment programs organized by either the government or Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) to educate people on the rights of children and the Child Rights Act;
- iii. There is a serious phobia for the law by major Islamic organizations in the country.
- iv. The increase in number of poor beggar's children in Nigerian cities, the number of children without basic education, and the number of children in one form of servitude or the other indicates the nation's poor level of development.

7.0 Recommendations

- 1. Kano State should be more serious when it comes to implementation of the law. Strong implementing mechanisms should be put in place in order to ensure proper dispensation of justice to the children. More shelters, counselling and rehabilitation centres should be built to cater for children left at the mercy of the public. The children's home should be more equipped to cater for the children. Proper awareness by both the government and the civil society organizations should be created on the need of fosterage in order to give more children care and sense of belonging.
- 2. Government should organize enlightenment programs as the major bottle neck for the acceptability of the Act is lack of education and awareness and the central belief that it gives children freedom to go against their parents.

⁷⁴ O. S. Akinwumi, (n.16), 391

3. Government should stand up to its primary task of improving social standards of children and people in general, by securing the polity, educating them and so on, as part of the promises it always makes at the point of campaign.
4. Parents and Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) should also help the government in discharging the above responsibilities.
5. More Legislations and policies aimed to prevent and respond to various abuses, holding perpetrators accountable and protecting children should be put in place.

8.0 Conclusion

With the Child Rights Act, 2003, Nigeria has a future. Kano state after persistent pressure from Civil Society Organizations at the tail end of the previous administration decided to pass into law the Kano State Child Protection Law 2022. Despite numerous provisions contained in the law to protect the child, it also has certain challenges that seems to hinder its smooth operation in the State. Factors contributing to the problem include but not limited to poverty, lack of access to quality education, cultural norms, and socio-economic issues all contributed to the high number of out-of-school children and at the risk faced by children in Kano. This paper was able to bring those challenges and also proffer workable recommendations for the proper and effective implementation of the law in the State. Lastly, the more the State invests in its children, the more it is investing in its future. No sustainability would reasonably be achieved if there are no responsible persons to manage tomorrow's resources. The quality of the State's future is directly proportional to the quality of its children today.